

RELATIONSHIP OF FORM AND MEANING OF LEGAL TERMS IN UZBEK AND GERMAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Linguistic units usually serve to express common objects and concepts, as well as specific concepts used in a specific field of human activity: science and technology, military, medicine, art, and other fields.

“Special purpose language” - MMT, formed in world linguistics

(Language for Specific Purposes-LSP, Yazik dlya spetsialnix seley - YASS) theory somewhat expresses the function and essence of terminological field units in language.

Keywords: specific lexemes, zoology or botany, minor crime; a serious crime, inheritance, theft - property. claim property; exhibition - instructional show.

Introduction

Due to the influence of interlinguistic factors such as the specific features of the lexical layer of each field, the fact that the lexical composition is different from each other, and the presence of specific lexemes of each field, only some types of meaningful communication are clearly visible in one or another field. For example, in the field of medicine, antonymy is extremely active (healthy-sick, alive-dead), but it is hardly found in zoology or botany. Based on this point of view, if we turn to our research object, we can talk about the following situations.

As a result of the analysis of the terms in the legal terminological system of the Uzbek language, it was found that they have a hyponymic relationship with each other. For example, a number of terms were created using the term crime: a crime with a low social risk; a minor crime; serious crime; intentional crime; a crime committed due to carelessness, etc.

So, the term participation appears as a hyponym of the hyperonym of crime.

The Main Findings and Results

A large number of terms related to economic crimes in the German language can be cited as an example. For example, Finanzier (financier), Notar (notary), Eindringling (raider), Plünderer (robber), Wilderer (poacher), Schmuggler (contraband), Drogenabhängiger (drug addict), Bestechung (bribery), Raub (robbery), Erpressung (extortion) (pledge), Schenkung (gift), Kommanditgesellschaft (limited partnership), Gesellschaft mit beschränkter

Haftung (limited liability company), Geldstrafe (fine), Freiheitsstrafe (imprisonment), Drogenabhängigkeit (drug addiction), Erpressung (extortion), Raub (robbery), Wirtschaftsgericht (business court), Verfahrensnachfolge (succession of proceedings), Staatspflicht (state duty), Wirtschaftsvertrag (business contract), Wirtschaftsgesellschaft (business society), Wirtschaftsrecht (business right) etc.

Synonymy of legal terms in Uzbek and German languages.

In Uzbek linguistics, synonymy is one of the more deeply studied issues. In works dedicated to the research of field terminologies, including the terminology of the legal field (M. Qasimova, Sh. Kochimov), synonymy is also mentioned separately. Accordingly, in our work, Uzbek legal terms were approached only from the point of view of systematic lexicology.

When it comes to the mutual relationship of lexical units, including terms, the issue of synonymy is also transverse. Because, whether we like it or not, especially in current Uzbek legal terminology, many concepts are expressed by two or more terms. Lexical synonyms (absolute) and variant types of synonyms are especially frequent in our research object.

When referring to the dictionaries and encyclopedias of legal terms, one can see that the series of lexical synonyms consists of not only two, but three or more terms: guardianship - patronage, witness - shahid, inheritance, theft - property. claim property; exhibition - instructional show, etc.

In many languages of the world, terminological units were created through the assimilation of words or forms from one language to another. Forms taken from a foreign language can form a synonym for certain forms that exist in one's own language. In the legal terminology of the German language, we can find terms with similar synonymous properties. For example Verbrechen-Straftat (crime), amnestieren-begnadigen (to pardon), Zeuge-Beobachter (witness), Scheidungskind-Trennungskind (divorced child), Verhör, Ermittlung (investigation, questioning), Freiheitsstrafe - Gefängnis- Haft (imprisonment), Entlassung - bedingte Verurteilung - bedingte Entlassung (conditional release), Begnadigung -Amnestie (amnesty), Vormundschaft -Sponsoring (sponsorship, guardianship) and others.

As in other terminological fields, in Uzbek legal terminology, a synonymous series consisting of proper and non-proprietary terms is often found. In this, the synonymy of lexical units of the Russian-international and own (some of them are Persian or Arabic) layers is especially noticeable.

At the same time, it can be seen that the synonymy of singular and compound terms is used a lot in legal terminology:

Consultant - chairman of the meeting;

Support - protection;

Correspondence - contact paper;

To acquit - to be found not guilty

It should be noted that it has become a habit for combined terms to become synonyms:

ehtiyot sudya – zapas sudya (reserve judge);

kafolatda turish – kafillikda bo‘lish (to be surety)

payli shirkat – hissadorlik shirkati (joint stock company).

qayta ro‘yxatga olish – qayta ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazish (re-registration) [1].

So, the active method that creates synonyms in the current Uzbek legal terminology is kalka.

Now let’s pay attention to the situation in German.

In the German language, the synonyms of legal terms are very developed, and the list of such words can be continued not only as international words, but also based on the internal possibilities of the German lexicology:

Experte-Fachman-Sachverständiger

Beschwerde-Klage (complaint)

amnestieren-begnadigen-expulpiieren(q)

Beschluss-Entscheidung-Resolution-Übereinkunft-Entschluss-Geheiß
(decision)

Delikt-Verbrechen-Vergehen-Straftat-Gesetzverstoß (crime)

Erkenntnis-Aufschluss-Beurteilung-Bewertung-Einsicht (recognition)

illegal-gesetzeswidrig-ungesetzlich (illegal)

Pflicht-Verpflichtung(duty)

Haft-Arrest-Gefangenschat-Gewahrsam-Knast (arrest)

Ausstand-Streik-Arbeitsniederlegung-Kampfmaßnahme (strike)

So even now synonyms are widely used in regulatory documents in both languages. Therefore, the documents of legal authorities cannot fully justify themselves at the moment, the rule of uniformity of terms is not followed. This can be seen in many examples:

single tax;

age of marriage, age of majority;

administrator, head of administration, manager

justice, legal trial

consulate, consulate, representative office, etc.

In German, we can cite the following examples:

Heiratsalter, Volljährigkeit (age of marriage, age of majority);

Administrator, Verwaltungsleiter, Manager (Administrator, head of administration, manager);

Justiz, Gerichtsverfahren (Justice, court proceedings);

Konsulat, Repräsentanz usw. (consulate, representative office, etc).

As a result of our observations, it became clear that both in Uzbek and in German, differences in the terminology of regulatory documents in the legislation are increasing due to words that are not standardized in the field of law: in Uzbek, goods are goods, integral goods; zone - circle, area; subsidy - providing additional funds, filling the gap Nemis tilida esa Zone - Kreis, Territorium (Zona - doira, hudud);

Subvention - Bereitstellung zusätzlicher Mittel, Füllen der Lücke (Subsidy - providing additional funds, filling the gap);

It should be noted that variant type of synonymy is also widespread in Uzbek and German legal terminology. The linguist G. Gulyamova explains that there are two types of such variant terms:

1. Variability of one-component terms: guaranty - guarantee, distrust - distrust, theft - theft, price-price-value, ignorance, etc.

2. Variant terms with two or more components, i.e. compound terms: justice - fair trial, - judicial review, financial bodies - financial bodies, private decision - separate decision, jurisconsult - legal consultant, etc [2].

“Legal terms,” one of the brochures states, ‘must clearly express unambiguous ideas, phrases should be extremely clear and fluent, content reflected in the expressed text should not be ambiguous, legal terminologies should be stable, and their use should be independent. (emphasis - G.G.), should meet the requirements of a simple and understandable structure of legal terms” [3].

Let’s compare the variant status of German synonyms.

1. In the German language, there are many synonymous cases of one-component words (Variation einkomponentiger Terme): Pflicht-Verpflichtung (duty), Staatsangehörige-Staatsbürgerin (female citizen), gesetzeswidrig-ungesetzlich (illegal), verhaften-inhaftieren (arrest).

2. Synonyms in the German language have arisen mainly lexically, at the expense of the rich internal possibilities of this language:

Regierung-Führung-Herrschaft(power)

Strafe-Maßregelung-Sühne-Vergeltung (punishment)

privat-individuell-persönlich (personal)

Votum-Stimme(sound)

amnestieren-begnadigen (to forgive)

Polysemy of terms. Another linguistic factor that indicates the relationship of words or terms is polysemy, that is, the existence of multiple meanings.

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